

Metal Derivatives of Antimony Thiocarboxylates. Part-II. Complexes of Beryllium-, Manganese-, Iron-, Cobalt-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Lead(II) with Antimony Hydrogen Bis(thiolactate)[†]

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Manuscript received 13 July 1989, revised 14 November 1990, accepted 4 March 1991

The complexes of bivalent Be, Mn, Fe, Co, Cu, Zn, Cd and Pb with antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analyses, magnetic measurements, infrared and electronic reflectance spectral data. The formation constants of the complexes formed by Be^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} ions have also been determined potentiometrically at 30 ± 0.05° using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti ($\mu = 0.01 M NaClO_4$).

THE reactions of various sulphur containing organic ligands like thiols, sulphides and disulphides with different metal ions have been reported^{1,2}, but very little work seems to have been carried out on metal derivatives of antimony thiocarboxylates. We report here the synthesis and structure of the complexes of Be^{II}, Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} with antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate). Formation constants of the Be^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes in aqueous medium have also been determined.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The ligand, antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was prepared and purified by known methods^{3,4}.

Antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate): Three equivalents of thiolactic acid were added slowly to a solution of antimony trichloride in dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting crystalline solid was washed with cold water and dried at 100–120°, m.p. 193°³.

The ligand was also prepared⁴ by boiling an aqueous solution of 0.66*N* thiolactic acid with antimony trioxide. The elemental analyses of the solids obtained by the two methods agreed with the composition C₆H₉O₄S₂Sb.

Cobalt(II), copper(II), manganese(II), iron(II) and nickel(II) sulphates, and lead(II) and cadmium(II) nitrates (all pure S. Merck) and beryllium(II) sulphate (Thomas Baker) were used after analysis.

pH was measured with a Philips PR 9405M pH meter with a glass (PV 9012) and calomel assembly. The instrument was calibrated using buffers of pH 4 and 9.2.

IR spectra (nujol and KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and diffused

reflectance spectra on a SP700 spectrophotometer with MgO as the reference (at I.I.T., Delhi). Magnetic susceptibility was measured using a Gouy balance and diamagnetic corrections were applied by the method of Lewis and Figgis.

Preparation of complexes: To a solution of the ligand (0.02 mol) in hot water (50 ml), an aqueous solution of the metal ion (0.01 mol) was added slowly with constant stirring. The complexes of Cu, Cd and Pb were precipitated immediately in the slightly acidic medium without neutralisation of hydrogen ions released from the ligand (pH 6–6.5, tested by pH-meter). However, in case of the Be, Mn, Fe, Co and Zn complexes, the solution was neutralised with a very dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. As soon as the mixture attained neutral point, addition of 1–2 drops more of NaOH solution separated the complex (pH 7.5–8). Since the complexes are highly insoluble, they were precipitated much before the solutions become highly alkaline to form hydroxy complexes or hydroxides. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water, alcohol and finally with ether. The product was dried under reduced pressure for ~1 h. The analytical data also confirms the composition of the complexes (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The ligand, antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) prepared by both the methods³⁻⁵ gave the similar analytical results as reported earlier.

The IR band at 2520 cm⁻¹ (S–H) of thiolactic acid¹ disappeared in the antimony compound and a new band appeared at 345–340 cm⁻¹ (Sb–S), indicating the formation of Sb–S linkage⁶. The ν_{OH} band appearing at 3400 cm⁻¹ in both thiolactic acid and

[†] A part of the paper was presented at the Symposium on 'Modern Trends in Coordination Chemistry' at Allahabad, 1979.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu_{\text{as CO}}$	$\nu_{\text{s CO}}$	ν_{MO}
		M	Sb	S	C	H				
Be(C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	White	—	—	18.53 (19.17)	20.21 (21.53)	1.92 (2.39)	Diamag.	1 570	1 380	420
Mn(C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	Black	7.45 (7.68)	—	17.04 (17.94)	19.48 (20.14)	1.94 (2.23)	6.1	1 570	1 380	425
Fe(C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	Brown	7.40 (7.80)	—	16.83 (17.92)	19.18 (20.12)	2.02 (2.23)	4.56	1 545	1 360	428
Co(C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	Brown	8.45 (8.20)	—	17.02 (17.84)	19.79 (20.03)	1.48 (2.22)	4.79	1 580	1 390	430
Cu ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	Black	15.26 (16.14)	—	15.80 (16.30)	20.98 (18.30)	2.35 (2.03)	Diamag.	1 570	1 380	425
Zn(C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	White	7.98 (9.01)	—	16.65 (17.61)	17.48 (19.85)	1.94 (2.20)	Diamag	1 550	1 340	425
Cd(C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	White	16.08 (14.55)	29.75 (31.53)	16.10 (16.48)	17.82 (18.64)	2.22 (2.07)	Diamag.	1 545	1 380	430
Pb(C ₆ H ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₂	White	23.2 (23.9)	29.65 (28.02)	13.74 (14.67)	15.52 (16.60)	1.56 (1.84)	Diamag.	1 510	1 350	420

the organic antimony compound shows the undeprotonation of OH group.

The fact that ν_{CO} bands of thiolactic acid at 1 715 and 1 680 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1 625 and 1 450 cm⁻¹ in organic antimony compound and further to 1 510–1 580 and 1 340–1 390 cm⁻¹ in the complexes under investigation, may be interpreted in terms of acetate group functioning as a bidentate ligand⁷. A band at 430–420 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ mode as suggested by Mishra and Mohapatra⁸.

The diamagnetic nature of the copper complex indicates strong spin-spin interaction between the copper atoms. The electronic spectrum of the copper complex showed a band at 24 390 cm⁻¹ indicating the spin-spin pairing⁹. The absence of bands at 15 750 and 19 370 cm⁻¹ rules out the planar geometry for the copper complex¹⁰. The analytical data, insolubility, high m.p., diamagnetism, visible spectra and the presence of bridging carboxylate groups suggest a tetrahedral polymeric structure for the copper complex.

The spectrum of the Fe^{II}-antimony bis(thiolactate) complex showed two weak bands at 11 770 cm⁻¹ which could be attributed to the transition ⁶T_{2g}→⁵E_g. In the Mn^{II} complex, two weak bands observed at 30 310 and 33 900 cm⁻¹ correspond to ⁶A_{1g}→⁴E_g (D) and ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g} (P) transitions respectively¹². Mn^{II} high-spin complexes have also been suggested by Figgis¹³.

Magnetic moments of the Mn^{II}, Fe^{II} and Co^{II} complexes were found to be 6.1, 4.56 and 4.79 B.M. respectively, indicating the formation of spin-free complexes¹³. All other complexes are diamagnetic. The complexes did not melt even up to 280° and decomposed at higher temperature.

Formation constants of complexes : The pH-titrations of the ligand (3×10⁻³M) were carried out in the absence and presence of the metal ion (5×10⁻⁴M) against 0.4N sodium hydroxide solution. Appropriate quantity of NaClO₄ (2M) was added to maintain the ionic strength at 0.1M.

Dissociation constant of the ligand, antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was determined by differential method¹⁴ and the value was found to be 3.162×10⁻⁶. Metal-ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting the values \bar{n} and pL, and stepwise formation constant (K) was determined using the following techniques¹⁵⁻¹⁷: (i) interpolation of half \bar{n} values, (ii) pointwise calculation method and (iii) curve fitting method. The values of log K for the complexes came out to be 2.76 (Be^{II}), 3.40 (Co^{II}), 3.85 (Ni^{II}) and 2.68 (Zn^{II}). Thus, the order of stability was Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Be^{II} > Zn^{II}.

It was not possible to determine the formation constant of the complexes of the other metal ions as the precipitation started from the very beginning.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Chairman of the Department for facilities. Two of the authors (S.L. and H.K.S.) are also thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial help.

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